

Influence of various coating techniques on the corrosion resistive behavior in Ringer's solution

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Abstract : Sol-gel silica glass has a significant effect on the microstructural and mechanical development of the implant materials. Sol-gel method is a versatile method to develop different types of oxide coatings on a large, curved substrates with high homogeneity and low sintering temperatures. In order to enhance the corrosion resistance behavior various types of oxide based, hybrid coatings have been studied. There are a number of interesting studies including the biological functions; biomineralisation with excellent bioactive ability and mechanical strength makes it suitable for biomedical applications. The aim of the work is to enhance the corrosion resistive behavior of the coatings using different strategies such as EPD method, spin coating and biomimetic coating. Silica glass is prepared at a molar ratio of H₂O/TEOS (Tetra Ethyl Ortho Silicate) and the obtained powder was characterized by FT-IR, XRD and SEM analysis. It was found that the sol-gel spin coatings have shown excellent thermal stability, oxidation control and enhanced corrosion resistance on metal substrates. The ability to passivate the metal substrates during coating has pronounced effect on corrosion resistance. The corrosion resistance behavior of the coatings was determined by (1) open-circuit potential versus time of exposure, (2) electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, (3) cyclic polarization in Ringer's solution.

Keywords : Impedance, polarization, spin coating, electrophoretic.

Introduction

For the past few decades, extensive research have been carried out on biomaterials related products due to their obvious use as replacement materials of various body parts or even organs. Metals are used in the human body for orthopaedic purposes and their degradation by corrosion and wear must be negligible, so that they can be used for various practical applications. Implants such as titanium, cobalt-chromium alloys and stainless steel have been used in more investigations because they have superior mechanical properties^{1,2}. However, metallic materials are susceptible to corrosive attack by body fluids, with subsequent release of metallic ions which might cause adverse effects to the surrounding tissues. The corrosion of the stainless steel implant releases metal ions such as Fe, Ni and Cr, which produce local systematic effects and thereby plays a role in prosthetic loosening.

Moreover, metallic surfaces are in general not adequately bioactive and surface treatment is usually needed to enhance the bioactivity so as to improve osseointegration with bone tissues³. One way of minimizing the oxidation

of the metal is by applying a protective coating on the metal surface. Inorganic coatings with vitreous structure have been widely used as protective coatings for metals and alloys, tending to improve the chemical and physical properties of the metallic substrate surfaces⁴. Calcium phosphate bioceramics has a unique characteristic for bone substitution compared with other biomaterials. They have such compositional resemblance to bone mineral that they induce a biological response similar to the one generated during bone remodeling.

Several types of methods have been adopted for the preparation of coatings, such as electrophoretic, plasma spray, CVD, sol-gel etc. Among them, the sol-gel process lies in tailoring the functional properties of coatings by changing the precursors, thermal treatments or addition of particles in sol. The main advantage of the process is the ability to form inorganic structures at a relatively low temperature and to produce thin homogeneous films on a large scale⁵. Studies on EPD on different implant alloys have been reported by several investigators and comprehensively reviewed by Sridhar *et al.*⁶. The

influence of both EPD and spin coatings over the implants are essential to study the effective implementation in the biocompatibility of the coatings.

In the present investigation, two coating methods such as spin and electrophoretic coatings have been proposed. The merits and demerits of both EPD and spin coatings is the major objective of this paper. The cracking as well as adhesion, durability of the coating in terms of corrosion resistance have been compared.

Experimental

Pure silica gel was prepared by using tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) as a silica precursor and the reactivity of TEOS towards water ($\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{TEOS}$) was modified at a molar ratio of 12 : 1. 1 M HNO_3 was used to decrease the pH of the silica sol solution to its isoelectric point. FT-IR is recorded using Shimadzu model 8300 spectrophotometer, Japan with the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} . The synthesized powder was characterized by XRD and it was recorded in an X-ray diffractometer (Seifert/Job-Debyerex-2002) with a step size of 0.02 ° and a scan rate of 1°/min with Cu K α radiation (1.54056 Å) for the identification of phase formation.

Development of coatings :

For spin coating, the sol was spun on the polished 316L SS substrates by the spin coating method at a constant speed of 2000 rpm/min at room temperature. Suspension for EPD coating was prepared by weighing 3 g of silica powder in 100 ml isopropyl alcohol and allowed to stand overnight. The coatings were deposited on the implant surface at a constant voltage of 60 V at 3 min and sintered at 600 °C.

Electrochemical investigation of the coatings :

Ringer's solution (8.6 g/L NaCl, 0.66 g/L $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 0.60 g/L KCl), which simulates body fluid conditions, was used as the electrolyte in the evaluation of the electrochemical behavior of the silica coated 316L SS. Platinum foil and 316L SS were used as the auxiliary and working electrode, respectively. Electrochemical Impedance Study (EIS) measurements were carried out using Gill AC potentiostat/galvanostat frequency response analyzer (ACM Instruments, UK). A perturbation AC potential of amplitude 10 mV over the frequency range from 10,000 Hz to 0.1 Hz was applied. Both Nyquist and

Bode plots were analyzed by a software analyzer to determine the parameters such as charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}). Thickness of the coatings was measured by using a sense probe of the ELCA-D meter, Germany. Hardness of the coating is measured by using Vicker's nano indentation method.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the FT-IR spectra of silica sample sintered at 900 °C. All the silica spectrum showed characteristic Si-O⁻ absorption bands at 788 cm^{-1} , 954 cm^{-1} and 1080 cm^{-1} respectively. The band at 788 cm^{-1} are attributed to the ring structure of the SiO_4 tetrahedral and the band at 1080 cm^{-1} is assigned to Si-O-Si stretching vibration. The band at 1650 cm^{-1} is attributed to the H-O-H deformation band indicates the presence of incorporated water in the SiO_2 network. A broad peak was observed at 3450 cm^{-1} which was attributed to hydroxyl (OH^-) groups on the surface of silicone. This could be due to the formation of silica gel through hydrolysis and condensation of TEOS.

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of silica powder.

Fig. 2 shows the XRD spectrum for the silica samples sintered at 900 °C. From the spectrum, it was confirmed the silica phase was completely formed without other secondary phase. The amorphous hump at 20.865 at the (*h k l*) value of (1 0 0) was confirmed the formation of silica. No other peak other than silica was observed in the XRD spectrum.

Both powder as well as the sol (without drying) were used for electrophoretic and spin coating respectively. The coating developed by EPD was sintered at 600 °C

Fig. 2. XRD spectra of silica powder.

and was evaluated for its corrosion resistive property in Ringer’s solution. The coating derived from spin coating was first dried in an oven at 100 °C for 15 min and finally, it was sintered in a vacuum furnace at the temperature of 600 °C. This could be done for the spin coated substrate, in order to avoid thermal mismatch between the coating and the metallic substrate. For the spin coating, the deposition of silane sol-gel coatings generally occurs in four stages⁷ such as hydrolysis of the silicon alkoxides, condensation, growth of the particles and agglomeration of the silica particles. For EPD coating, the silica powder was directly deposited on the metal substrates and finally sintered. From the figure (not shown here), it was evident that the spin coated silica has more corrosion resistance behavior than the EPD coated implant. The breakdown value (E_b) of 532 mV was observed for the spin coated and the E_b of 410 mV was observed for the EPD coated silica over the implant. Thus, the E_b value for both EPD and spin was higher than the uncoated implant (320 mV). The passivation potential (E_p) for the spin coated implant has revealed a value of 219 mV, which is higher than the other coating, which has shown a less passivation potential as -60 mV. Table 1 represents the electrochemical parameters of the silica coating developed by various methods.

The results shown in cyclic polarization corroborate the impedance analysis (Fig. 3), the spin coated implant

Fig. 3. Nyquist plot for the silica coating developed by different methods.

have shown the higher R_{ct} value of 3.134×10^5 ohm than the EPD coated silica implant (2.138×10^5 ohm). Hence, with the increase in R_{ct} value and the decrease in C_{dl} value for the spin coated implant have shown more corrosion resistance behavior. Concerning corrosion science, a lot of efforts have been made to apply these materials as adhesion promoters between metallic substrates and the organic coatings used for protection against corrosion phenomena. Hence, we evaluated the adhesion of the coating over the implant and found that the spin coated implant have shown a maximum hardness value of 5.8 Gpa than the EPD coated implant, where it has shown a hardness value of 1.08 Gpa only. Hence, the adhesion phenomena of spin coating may be due to self passivation of metal with the silica sol. In fact, it is necessary to have a sufficient number of silanol (Si-OH) groups to interact with the metal substrate⁸, because only the hydrolyzed species can lead to the formation of strong covalent bonds with the metal substrate. Thus, the silanol groups can interact, not only among themselves, but also with the hydroxyl groups in equilibrium on metal substrate. This is a critical point for the deposition of silane sol-gel films.

Table 1

Sample	E_b (mV)	E_p (mV)	$R_{ct} \times 10^5$ (Ohms)	$C_{dl} \times 10^{-6}$ (Faraday)	Hardness (Gpa)	Thickness (μm)
Blank	320	-80	0.9819	3.380	-	-
EPD coating	410	-60	2.138	2.998	1.08	23
Spin coating	532	219	3.134	2.638	5.8	12

The metal surface has to be rich in hydroxyl groups to permit the adsorption of the silanols to occur.

Coating thickness is an important parameter in bioapplications, since, thick coatings tend to crack under loading. A highly crystalline coating is more stable on heating, but can give rise to fragmented particles. Whereas, a thin film coating is subject to slow degradation during long term and facilitates formation of new bone. An increase in coating thickness results in less degradation, but would increase the problems related to mechanical failure of the coating. Hence, spin coating may overcome the aforementioned drawbacks and achieve more adherent with less coating thickness and free from delamination.

Conclusion

(i) Pure silica gel was prepared and characterized by FT-IR and XRD analysis. The influence of sol-gel spin coating and powder electrophoretic coating was studied on 316L SS implant. The coating was evaluated in terms of corrosion resistance capacity in a physiological medium, coating thickness and hardness.

(ii) Both the coatings have shown corrosion resistance behavior, but the one developed by spin coating have

shown more resistance, because of self passivation of metal with the sol.

(iii) During spin coating, the interaction between silane molecules and metal hydroxides was taken place. Upon drying, condensation reactions occur between the Si-OH groups of the silanol and the M-OH hydroxides of the metal, leads to the formation of more adherent and self passivated implant with more corrosion resistance.

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